

PRINCIPALS TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLE AND SCHOOL PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined the extent to which principals' transformational leadership predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. The population of the study comprised all 274 schools with principals in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, from which a sample of 30 schools, with principals and 150 teachers, was selected using a purposive sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed instrument entitled 'Transformational Leadership Questionnaire' (PTLQ) and a proforma entitled "Students' Academic Performance Proforma" (SAPP). The collated data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The formulated hypotheses were tested using regression analysis. Findings from the study revealed that the inspirational motivation component of transformational leadership significantly predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. However, intellectual stimulation, individualised consideration, and the idealised influence component of transformational leadership do not significantly predict schools' productivity in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings, the study it was concluded that the inspirational motivation component of transformational leadership significantly predicts school productivity. It is recommended that the State Secondary Education Board should train principals on transformational leadership skills and ensure teachers are inspired and adequately motivated to improve student academic performance.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Secondary Education, School productivity

Introduction

School productivity is a multidimensional concept that refers to the efficiency and effectiveness with which educational institutions utilise resources to achieve desired academic and non-academic outcomes. Scholars have defined school productivity in various ways, emphasising aspects such as student performance, teacher effectiveness, resource utilisation, and overall institutional efficiency. **Hanushek (2022)** described school productivity as the ability of schools to maximise student

learning outcomes given available resources, including funding, teacher quality, and instructional time. Similarly, **Levin and Belfield (2023)** argued that school productivity is not merely about financial input but also involves the optimal allocation of human and material resources to enhance students' cognitive and social development.

A widely accepted measure of school productivity is student achievement, often assessed through standardised test scores, graduation rates, and college readiness. **Hattie (2023)** emphasises that productive schools are those that implement evidence-based teaching strategies, provide continuous professional development for teachers, and foster a supportive learning environment. Furthermore, **Scheerens (2022)** highlights that school productivity should not be solely measured by academic success but also by students' ability to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and social skills, which contribute to lifelong learning and employability. This broader perspective aligns with the view of **Fullan (2023)**, who asserts that productive schools are those that cultivate a culture of innovation, collaboration, and adaptability among students and teachers.

Principals' administrative proficiency is argued to be one of the key determinants of school productivity (Ochoyi, 2023). The role of school principals in shaping the educational experience and outcomes of students cannot be overstated. Principals serve as the instructional leaders of their schools, responsible for setting the tone, vision, and direction for the entire school community. The position of a principal remains a fundamental balance to a school system because he oversees the school, regulating laws, supervision, budgetary provisions, planning and control, as well as execution and implementation of school policies and programmes. When any section of these administrative responsibilities is inappropriately managed, issues arise that may contribute to the ineffectiveness of other personnel or inadequacy in the management of school plans and instructional facilities and, in turn, may constitute a clog to the wheel of school productivity.

A close observation of some secondary schools in Nigeria, including those in Akwa Ibom State, reveals teaching and learning environments that are inadequate to guarantee quality learning outcomes. More worrisome is the unacceptable level of students' failure in internal and external examinations. The incessant cases of administrative conflicts between the principal and the teachers in some schools have undermined the commitment of some of the teachers to the students. This situation may arguably have led to poor productivity, as evident in the increasing number of students who failed to reach the requirements for tertiary education. Nevertheless, since effective leadership is foundational to educational outcomes, it becomes essential to ask: could the principal's leadership style be responsible for the productivity of the schools?

Over the years, diverse leadership models have been applied by principals in schools, and different results have been achieved. One of such leadership model, believed to have a significant impact on teachers' performance, assists in solving various problems in school, enhances organisational culture, and also supports the development of a quality school: the transformational leadership model (Raharja *et al.*, 2022). Transformational leadership is a leadership style that focuses on inspiring and motivating followers to achieve a shared vision through personal growth and development. Transformational leadership emphasises motivation, collaboration, and creativity among subordinates to drive meaningful change within an organisation. Ereh *et al.* (in Ughamadu and Ujunwa, 2021) described transformational leadership in schools as a principal's ability to lead effectively by fostering teamwork, modelling ethical behaviour, and motivating staff members to collaborate towards achieving positive institutional change. Transformational leaders are characterised by four key attributes: idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration. They acknowledge the perspectives and needs of subordinates while delegating authority, which fosters a harmonious organisational environment. Moreover, transformational leaders possess the ability to empower their followers, set ambitious goals, and prioritise personal development (Ngemunang, 2019). Their influence extends to inspiring subordinates to exhibit a strong commitment to organisational objectives.

Transformational leadership style is a leadership approach that inspires and motivates followers to exceed expectations by fostering a shared vision, intellectual stimulation, and individualised support. Transformational leadership is defined by its ability to inspire and motivate individuals to attain exceptional results while fostering a culture of creativity and innovation. The concept was first introduced by **Burns (1978)**, who distinguished between transformational and transactional leadership. Burns described transformational leaders as those who engage with their followers in a way that raises motivation, morale, and performance, whereas transactional leaders focus on exchanges and rewards for task completion. Building on this foundation, **Bass (2020)** expanded the theory by identifying key dimensions of transformational leadership, including idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration.

Intellectual stimulation is the character of a transformational leader who can encourage his subordinates to solve problems carefully and rationally. In addition, this character encourages subordinates to find new, more effective ways of solving problems. Furthermore, transformational leaders are leaders who can encourage (stimulate) subordinates to always be creative and innovative. Andriani *et al.* (2018) believe that principals who encourage intellectual stimulation will allow teachers to ask new questions and alter their values and beliefs. This practice removes outdated and inappropriate problem-solving methods and employs new and more effective solutions.

Inspirational motivation means the character of a leader who can apply high standards but at the same time can encourage subordinates to achieve these standards. A character like this can generate high optimism and enthusiasm from subordinates. In other words, transformational leaders always inspire and motivate their subordinates. Inspirational motivation is the behaviour that always provides challenges for the staff or the employee and shows the meaning of their jobs for the staff or the employee as well. According to Vijian and Wahab (2020), motivational inspiration describes the process by which leaders motivate their followers, encourage them to improve their performance, and allow them to achieve organisational goals. Leaders who inspire motivation demonstrate the way in which employees can complete a task more easily and encourage shared goals concerning what is right and important. Using this approach and by giving tasks meaning, leaders can inspire and motivate their followers to complete their tasks.

Individualised consideration means the character of a leader who can understand the individual differences of his subordinates. Individual consideration refers to the process of understanding each employee, sharing their problems, and addressing their individual needs (Vijian and Wahab, 2020). Transformational leaders account for their employees' uniqueness and respect the differences among their followers. In other words, principals enhance, expand and develop teachers' potential (Vijian and Wahab, 2020). In this case, transformational leaders are willing and able to listen to aspirations, educate, and train subordinates. In addition, a transformational leader can see potential achievements and the developing needs of subordinates and facilitate them. In other words, transformational leaders can understand and appreciate subordinates based on the needs of subordinates and pay attention to the desires of subordinates to excel and develop.

Idealised influence means that a transformational leader must be charismatic, able to "bewitch" subordinates to react to follow the leadership. Charisma involves being the best example for subordinates, encouraging employees to "do the right thing", and a readiness to take risks for the good of the organisation (Vijian and Wahab, 2020). The charismatic leader is respected and trusted by their followers. Leaders hope to be thought of as an example by their followers. Leaders of this type always put the interests of their followers before self-interest and are willing to share risks with followers. In concrete form, this charisma is shown through the behaviour of understanding the vision and mission of the organisation, having a firm stance, being committed and consistent with every decision that has been taken, and respecting subordinates. In other words, transformational leaders become role models who are admired, valued, and followed by their subordinates. A leader shows or demonstrates commitment to the organisation through a behaviour that is observed by the staff. A leader is a motivator who always tries to raise the enthusiasm and optimism of the staff.

In Anambra State, Nigeria, Obidi *et al.* (2020) examined the principals' leadership style and business studies teachers' productivity in secondary schools in the Awka education zone, Anambra State, and found a negligible negative relationship between principals' transformational leadership style and productivity of business studies teachers and a significant positive relationship between principals' transactional leadership style and productivity of business studies teachers. Another study in Ekiti State found no significant difference between the mean scores of principals and teachers as regards the extent to which principals' transformational leadership practices enhance goal achievement (Ogwa 2021). In his research on teacher productivity, Okoko *et al.* (2023) found that transformational leadership practices actively impacted teachers' commitment, which in turn improves student academic performance in secondary school. In Kenya, Muia *et al.* (2017) found that principals' inspirational motivation has a significantly positive influence on students' performance at KCSE examinations. Musyoki *et al.* (2021), in their study on the influence of principals' inspirational motivation on student academic performance in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) in Makueni County, however, found a negative and strong correlation between inspirational motivation and students' KCSE performance.

Statement of the Problem

The secondary school system ought to be a place where school principals interrelate among colleagues; create cordial collaboration with the teaching personnel; and curriculum instructions are transferred using the best-managed school plans and instructional facilities within a safe and secure environment. However, some schools have incidentally become a haven of misconduct and insecurity. More worrisome is the overcrowded classrooms resulting from inadequate classroom blocks. Some teachers, however, insinuate that overcrowding of the classrooms has little influence on students as compared with the inability of the principals to commit school resources to the acquisition of instructional facilities for easy instructional transfer.

More disturbing are the incessant cases of principal-teacher administrative conflicts occasioned by the authoritarian leadership model utilised by the principals, with the slogan “wait for your turn”. This has severed expected collaboration, undermined commitment, and promoted discord among personnel, which often results in a decrease in the performance of teachers. This is evidenced by the massive failure of students in some schools in the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). Similarly, the leadership approaches and behavioural disposition of some principals have discouraged active participation of teachers in decision-making processes, their creativity and innovation, and effective feedback mechanisms, thus promoting unnecessary tension which could negatively impact teaching and learning and, ultimately, students' performance.

Nevertheless, since school productivity cannot happen spontaneously except through the anchoring of the coordinates by the principal, it becomes essential to ask, could the principal's transformational leadership style influence secondary schools' productivity?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent to which principals' transformational leadership predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Question

To what extent does principals' transformational leadership predict school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

To guide this study, a null hypothesis was formulated thus;
Principals' transformational leadership does not significantly predict school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Method

This study was carried out to establish how transformational leadership behaviour contributes to school productivity. It employed an ex post facto research design. The target population consisted of 274 principals in public secondary schools. The researcher sampled 30 public schools and 150 teachers using a purposive sampling technique. The schools were selected on the criteria that the principal has served in the same school for not less than three years. NECO-SSCE results of science students in 2024 were used for the judgement of the school productivity based on students' academic performance.

For the selection of teachers to rate their principals, a purposive sampling approach was also adopted. Teachers were selected based on the criterion of having served under the same principal for at least three years. This selection criterion ensured that the teachers had a sufficient duration of interaction with the principal, providing them with a solid foundation for assessing the principal's transformational leadership style. A total of five teachers who met the criteria were randomly selected from each of the 30 schools, resulting in 150 teachers across the study.

To measure the school's productivity, the study used the performance of science students in the 2024 National Examination Council Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (NECO-SSCE). The main research instruments were a researcher-developed instrument entitled "Principals' Transformational Leadership Questionnaire" (PTLQ) and a proforma entitled "Students' Academic Performance Proforma" (SAPP). The hypotheses were tested at the .05 level of significance. The calculated probability value was less than the significance level; hence, the null

hypotheses were rejected, indicating that a significant difference exists. On the other hand, the calculated probability value was greater than the significance level; hence, the null hypotheses were retained, indicating that no significant difference exists.

The value of the beta (β) coefficient and correlation index (R) obtained in the regression model was used to answer the research question, and the hypothesis, which has to do with the determination of the extent to which the transformational leadership model predicts school productivity, is presented as follows:

Beta (β value)	Interpretation
+/- 0.81 to 0.100	Very high extent
+/- 0.61 to 0.80	High extent
+/- 0.41 to 0.100	Moderate extent
+/- 0.21 to 0.40	Low extent
+/- 0.00 to 0.20	Very low extent

The decision for the null hypothesis was based on the probability value (p-value). When the p-value was greater than .05 ($p > .05$), the null hypothesis was retained, showing that the result is statistically not significant, whereas when the p-value was less than the acceptable level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the result is statistically significant at the .05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question:

To what extent does the principals' transformational leadership model predict school productivity in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Multiple Regression Analysis for the Extent to which Transformational Leadership Approach Predict School Productivity in Public Secondary Schools

Model	R	R Square	Extent of Prediction	Remark
Transformational leadership	.823	.677	67.7%	High Extent
School productivity				

Source: Field Work (2024)

The entries in Table 1 reveal the R for the strength of the relationship and R^2 for the determination of the extent of the relationship to which transformational leadership style predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The R-value of .823 indicates a strong level of relationship between the two variables. The calculated R^2 of .677, which is the coefficient of determination,

indicates that 67.7% of school productivity is predicted by transformational leadership style. Therefore, the result means that the transformational leadership approach determines, to a high extent, school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis:

Secondary school principals' transformational leadership model on school productivity is not a significant predictor of school productivity in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2a: Regression Analysis of Principals' Transformational Leadership and School Productivity

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.007	4	2.502	13.115	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.769	25	.191		
	Total	14.776	29			

Mod		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.045	.618		3.310	.003
	Inspiration Motivation	.111	.035	.511	3.197	.004
	Individualization	.046	.036	.286	1.284	.211
	Consideration	.021	.031	.134	.663	.513
	Intellectual Stimulation	-.013	.029	-.060	-.465	.646

*Not significant at the P< .05 level

Source: Field Work (2024)

Table 2a shows that F and p-value are 13.115 and .000, respectively, at 4 and 25 degrees of freedom. The result is significant at .05; therefore, the null hypothesis, which claimed the secondary school principals' transformational leadership model on school productivity was not a significant predictor of school productivity in Akwa Ibom State, was rejected. In other words, the results indicate that principals' transformational leadership significantly predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

The table 2b shows the regression analysis of principals' transformational leadership, which covers the four principals' transformational leadership components, comprising inspirational motivation, individualised consideration, idealised influence, and intellectual stimulation, and school productivity. Each of these models has a p-value of .004, .211, .513, and .646, respectively. Among these transformational leadership models, it was shown that the p-values of individualised consideration, idealised influence, and intellectual stimulation (p-values .211, .513,

and .646) are greater than .05, implying that they were not statistically significant. Therefore, these transformational leadership components were not a significant predictor of school productivity in Akwa Ibom State. However, inspirational motivation with a p-value less than .05 was a significant predictor of school productivity in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, the regression equation for this study is school productivity = 2.045. Being +.111 of inspirational motivation, +.046 of individualised consideration, +.021 of idealised influence, and -.013 of intellectual stimulation.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study showed that individualisation consideration, idealised influence, and intellectual stimulation as models of transformational leadership were not statistically significant predictors of school productivity in Akwa Ibom State. However, the inspirational motivation transformational leadership model was a statistically significant predictor of school productivity. This implies that utilisation of the inspirational motivation leadership model significantly promotes school productivity. This is premised on the fact that inspirational motivation often involves the principals' ability to articulate a compelling vision, express confidence in teachers, and inspire enthusiasm. These behaviours are often visible to teachers and directly influence their engagement, commitment, and day-to-day performance. In contrast, the other components are less visible and longer-term in impact. For instance, idealised influence emphasises serving as a role model and may require some time to be visible to teachers. Intellectual stimulation, which involves encouraging innovation and critical thinking, may be limited by resources available in public schools. Individualised consideration, which requires personalised support and mentoring, may be difficult to implement due to large staff size, time constraints, and administrative workload.

The study, as supported by Musyoki *et al.* (2021) in their study on the influence of principals' inspirational motivation on student academic performance in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Examination (KCSE) in Makueni County, Kenya, showed a strong correlation between inspirational motivation and KCSE students' mean scores. The result indicated a strong correlation between inspirational motivation and students' KCSE performance. The findings also corroborated that of Okoko *et al.* (2023), which revealed that principals' transformational leadership practices positively enhance teachers' productivity. It was further found that principals' transformational leadership practices actively impacted teachers' commitment, which in turn improves student academic performance in secondary school. The findings also corroborate the findings of Muia *et al.* (2017) on the influence of principals' inspirational motivation on students' academic performance at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations in Mbooni West Sub-County, Kenya, which showed that intellectual stimulation has a significantly positive influence on students' performance at KCSE examinations.

The findings contradicted the findings of Obidi *et al.* (2020), which revealed that there is a negligible negative relationship between principals' transformational leadership style and productivity of business studies teachers in secondary schools in Awka education zone, Anambra State. It also contradicted the findings of Ogwa's (2021) study on the extent that principals use transformational leadership practices for goal achievement in secondary schools in Oye L.G.A., Ekiti State, Nigeria, with the major finding that principals use transformational leadership practices such as intellectual stimulation, idealised influence, inspirational motivation and individualised consideration but established no significant difference to goal achievement in secondary schools in Oye L.G.A., Ekiti State.

Conclusion/Recommendation

The study concluded that the inspirational motivation component of transformational leadership predicts school productivity in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. However, intellectual stimulation, individualised consideration, and idealised influence components of transformational leadership are not predictors of schools' productivity in Akwa Ibom State. From this finding and conclusion, it is therefore recommended that the State Secondary Education Board should train principals on transformational leadership skills and ensure teachers are inspired and adequately motivated to improve student academic performance.

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